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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF DICLOFENAC NIOSOMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

In order to establish and maintain drugs from any concentrations at target sites for a longer period of time, niosomes was formulated. The main aim of this study was to formulate niosomal suspension containing diclofenac sodium multilamellar vesicle (MLVs). Diclofenac is a drug with narrow therapeutic index and short biological half-life. This study was aimed at developing and optimizing niosomal formulation of diclofenac in order to improve its bioavailability. In evaluation study the effect of the varying composition of non ionic surfactant and cholesterol on the properties such as encapsulation efficiency, particle size and drug release were studied. Moreover, the release of the drug was also modified and extended over a period of 72 h in all formulations. Different ratios of cholesterol and surfactant (span 20, span 40 and span 60) were used. The optimized ratio was 1:2:1 with highest entrapment efficiency. The *in-vitro* release of the drug was consistent. The time course of drugs and their effects in the body are assessed through pharmacokinetics which was provided by mathematical basis. The data collected from the release were incorporated into release kinetic analyses which are Higuchi equation and Korsmeyer-Peppas equations. Further, release of the drug from the most satisfactory formulation NF-6 was evaluated through dialysis membrane to get the idea of drug release. The mechanism of drug release was governed by Peppas model.

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INTRODUCTION

The main goal of a site specific drug delivery system is not only to increase the selectivity and drug therapeutic index, but also to reduce the toxicity of the drug. At present no available drug delivery system achieves the site specific delivery with controlled release kinetics of drug in predictable manner.

Paul Ehrlich, in 1909, initiated the era of development for targeted delivery when he envisaged a drug delivery mechanism that would target directly to diseased cell. Since then, number of carriers was utilized to carry drug at the target organ/tissue, which include immunoglobulins, serum proteins, synthetic polymers, liposomes, microspheres, erythrocytes, niosomes etc. Among different carriers liposomes and niosomes are well documented drug delivery.

Drug targeting can be defined as the ability to direct a therapeutic agent specifically to desired site of action with little or no interaction with non target tissue. Niosomes or non-ionic surfactant vesicles are microscopic lamellar structures formed on admixture of non-ionic surfactant of the alkyl or dialkyl polyglycerol ether class and cholesterol with subsequent hydration in aqueous media. In niosomes, the vesicles forming amphiphile is a non-ionic surfactant such as Span – 60 which is usually stabilized by addition of cholesterol and small amount of anionic surfactant such as dicetyl phosphate. Schematic representation of a drug targeting through its linkage to niosome via antibody is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Niosome structure

These non ionic surfactant vesicles can entrap both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs, either in aqueous layer or in the vesicular membrane made of lipid materials, which can be used to prolong the circulation of the entrapped drugs. Due to the presence of non ionic surfactant and the lipid, there is a better targeting of drug(s) to tumour, liver and brain. Thus, they are useful in targeting of the drug for treating cancers, parasitic, viral and other microbial diseases more effectively. These non-ionic surfactant based vesicles (niosomes) are regarded either as a inexpensive alternative of non-biological origin to liposomes or perhaps as a carrier system of drug physically similar to liposome *in vivo*, with specific properties to attain different drug distribution and release characteristics.

Diclofenac belongs to non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). It works by blocking the action of cyclooxygenase. Cyclooxygenase is involved in the production of various chemicals in the body, some of which are known as prostaglandins. Prostaglandins are produced in response to injury or certain diseases and would otherwise go on to cause pain, swelling and inflammation. Diclofenac is used to relieve pain and inflammation in arthritic conditions. All the drugs in this group reduce inflammation caused by the body's own immune system and are effective pain killers. But it has several drawbacks such as narrow therapeutic index, short biological half-life. These factors necessitated niosomal formulation for diclofenac. As this dosage form would reduce the dosing frequency, hence better patient compliance. The present study was aimed with the formulation of niosomes of diclofenac followed by the evaluating parameters such as drug content, entrapment efficiency, particle size, shape, size distribution and *in vitro* drug release.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Diclofenac was obtained from Rantus Pharmaceuticals Hyderabad, India; Spans were obtained from Rolex chemical industries, Mumbai. Diethyl ether Methanol was obtained from S.D.Fine chemicals. All ingredients used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Niosomes

Niosomes containing diclofenac were prepared by modified ether injection technique using non ionic surfactant (span 60, span 40 and span 20) and cholesterol at different concentrations. Cholesterol and surfactant were dissolved in 6ml diethyl ether mixed with 2ml methanol containing weighed quantity of diclofenac. The resulting solution was slowly injected using micro syringe at a rate of 1ml/min into 15 ml of hydrating solution phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The solution was stirred continuously on magnetic stirrer and temperature was maintained

at 60-65°C. As the lipid solution was injected slowly into aqueous phase, the differences in temperature between phases cause rapid vaporization of ether, resulting in spontaneous vesiculation and formation of niosomes. Different batches of niosomes were prepared in order to select an optimized formula as per general method described above and proportion of surfactant and cholesterol for the preparations of niosomes is given in Table 1 and optimized niosomal formula are given in Table 2.

Table 1: Composition of surfactant and cholesterol for preparation of niosomes

S. No	Code	Surfactant	Drug: Surfactant: Cholesterol	Weight Taken (in mg)		
				drug	surfactant	cholesterol
01	NF-1	Span 60	1:1:1	200	200	200
02	NF-2		1:2:1	200	400	200
03	NF-3	Span 40	1:1:1	200	200	200
04	NF-4		1:2:1	200	400	200
05	NF-5	Span 20	1:1:1	200	200	200
06	NF-6		1:2:1	200	400	200

Table 2: Optimised formula for the niosome preparation

S. No	Formula	NF-2	NF-4	NF-6
01	Cholesterol	200 mg	200 mg	200 mg
02	Span 60	400 mg	----	----
03	Span 40	----	400 mg	----
04	Span 20	----	----	400 mg
05	Diclofenac	200	200	200
06	Methanol	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml
07	Diethyl ether	8 ml	8 ml	8 ml
08	Phosphate buffer(7.4)	15 ml	15 ml	15 ml

Drug Entrapment efficiency of niosomes

Entrapment efficiency of niosomes was determined by exhaustive dialysis method. The measured quantity of niosomal suspension was taken into a dialysis tube to which osmosis cellulose membrane was securely attached on one side. The dialysis tube was suspended in 100ml phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), which was stirred on a magnetic stirrer. The untrapped drug was separated from the niosomal suspension into the medium through osmosis cellulose membrane. At every hour entire medium (100ml) was replaced with fresh medium (for about 9-12h) till the

absorbance reached a constant reading indicating no drug is available in untrapped form. The niosomal suspension in the dialysis tube was further lysed with propane-1-ol and estimated the entrapped drug by UV spectrophotometric method at 274nm. The entrapment efficiency was calculated using following equation.

$$\text{Entrapment efficiency} = \frac{\text{Amount of entrapped drug}}{\text{Total amount of drug}} \times 100$$

Drug content

Niosomes preparation equivalent to 40mg of diclofenac was taken into a standard volume flask. Then they were lysed with 100ml of

propane-1-ol by shaking. Then 1ml of this was subsequently diluted with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The absorbance was measured at 274nm and calculated drug content from the calibration curve.

$$\% \text{ Drug content} = \frac{\text{Sample absorbance}}{\text{Standard absorbance}} \times \frac{\text{Standard dilution}}{\text{Sample dilution}} \times 100$$

Particle size and shape analysis

Particle size analysis was carried out using an optical microscope with a calibrated eyepiece micrometer. About 50 niosomes were measured individually, further microphotographs of optimized niosomes were taken by using 9 megapixel Sony digital camera. The microphotograph shown below is the optimised formula NF-6.

Fig.No.2: Size distribution of NF-6

Table 3: Evaluation parameters of niosomes

Sl. No	Formulation	Entrapment efficiency	Mean particle size $\mu\text{m} \pm \text{SD}$
01	NF-1	75.20%±0.51	4.73±0.35 μm .
02	NF-2	77.23%±0.43	4.60±0.49 μm .
03	NF-3	81.41%±0.46	4.57±0.51 μm .
04	NF-4	88.02%±0.39	4.75±0.46 μm .
05	NF-5	91.35%±0.28	4.30±0.71 μm .
06	NF-6	95.07%±0.35	4.22±0.47 μm .

In vitro release studies

The release of diclofenac from niosomal formulations were determined using membrane diffusion technique [6-7]. The niosomal formulation equivalent to 40mg of diclofenac was placed in a glass tube of diameter 2.5cm with an effective length of 8cm that was previously covered with soaked osmosis cellulose membrane, which acts as a donor compartment. The glass tube was placed in a beaker containing 100ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), which acted as receptor compartment. The whole assembly was fixed in

such a way that the lower end of the tube containing suspension was just touching (1-2mm deep) the surface of diffusion medium. The temperature of receptor medium was maintained at 37±100C and agitated at 100rpm speed using magnetic stirrer. Aliquots of 5ml sample were withdrawn periodically and after each withdrawal same volume of medium was replaced. The collected samples were analysed at 274nm in Double beam UV-VIS spectrophotometer using phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as blank.

Table 4: The kinetic analysis of niosomal formulation loaded with diclofenac sodium

Time (hrs)	\sqrt{t}	Log t	Amount released (mg)	% drug released	% drug to be released	Log % drug released	Log % drug to be released	$D^{1/3}$
1	1.0	0	8.9	17.8	82.2	1.2504	1.9148	4.266
2	1.414	0.301	16.58	33.16	66.84	1.5206	1.8250	4.001
4	2.0	0.602	27.9	55.2	44.8	1.7419	1.6512	3.745
6	2.449	0.778	33.9	67.07	32.93	1.8265	1.5175	3.098
8	2.828	0.903	48.56	96.07	3.93	1.9825	0.5943	1.769

Where, D – Percentage drug to be released, t – Time

Table 5: Data showing in vitro drug release model fitting kinetic parameters of NF1-NF6

Formulation Code	Cumulative % drug released vs time (zero order)		Cumulative % drug released vs square root of time(Higuchi's)		Log cumulative % Drug retained vs time (Kosermeier's peppas)		
	R	K	R	K	Slope(n)	R	K
NF-1	0.8445	1.3678	0.9876	10.123	0.7342	0.9768	5.0043
NF-2	0.8123	1.2368	0.9780	9.1345	0.6571	0.9859	5.8974
NF-3	0.8002	1.1789	0.9657	8.765	0.7143	0.9768	4.8791
NF-4	0.9467	1.0578	0.9863	7.653	0.6798	0.9961	4.2367
NF-5	0.8973	1.4200	0.9921	10.147	0.6609	0.9967	6.1562
NF-6	0.9124	1.4256	0.9965	10.189	0.6578	0.9978	6.2181

Graph 1: The zero-order kinetics (cumulative amount of diclofenac sodium released on y-axis vs. Time on x-axis) of the niosomal formulation NF-6.

Graph 2: Higuchi equation for diclofenac sodium niosomes (% diclofenac released on y-axis vs \sqrt{t} on x-axis)

Graph 3: The Korsmeyer-Peppas equation for diclofenac sodium niosomes (log diclofenac released on y-axis vs log time on x-axis)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Among the various methods, Modified ether injection method is widely used to prepare niosomes. The entrapment efficiency of niosomes prepared at varied concentration of surfactants: diclofenac, keeping cholesterol concentration constant are shown in Table 2.

In all the niosomes prepared with spans, as the concentration of surfactant increased drug entrapment efficiency increased. The encapsulation efficiency of niosomes is governed by the ability of formulation to retain drug molecules in the aqueous core or in the bilayer

membrane of the vesicles. Cholesterol improves the fluidity of the bilayer membrane and improves the stability of bilayer membrane in the presence of biological fluids such as blood/plasma. Among the spans, span 60 having high phase transition temperature (gel to liquid transformation) and having critical packing parameter (CPP) ranging from 0.5 to 1 entrap drug molecule without any cholesterol. The only drawback of span 60 vesicles was rapid leakage of drug from the vesicle because of high phase transition temperature. A small concentration of about 10-20% cholesterol was optimum to get stable vesicle

by abolishing the phase transition temperature resulting in stable niosomes avoiding drug leakage.

The study of drug release kinetics showed that majority of the formulations governed by Peppas model. The curve was obtained after plotting the cumulative amount of drug released from each formulation against time. Formulation NF-6 (87.21%) showed maximum release while other formulation showed less amount of drug release in 72h. Formulation NF-6 has highest correlation coefficient ($r = 0.9978$) value and follows drug release by Peppas model.

CONCLUSION

The incorporation of Diclofenac Sodium in the niosomal drug targeted delivery system was assumed to be more appropriate compared to the conventional drug delivery system.

The present study demonstrated the successful preparation of Diclofenac niosomes and their evaluation. Formulation NF-6 showed high entrapment efficiency ($95.07\% \pm 0.35$), particle size ($4.22 \pm 0.47 \mu\text{m}$) and drug release (87.21%) over 72 h. Hence it was considered to be good niosomal formulation with greater bioavailability. Diclofenac sodium was released slowly as the niosomes act as a depot and offer a controlled release.

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